

MAHALLA CONCEPT. HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF MAHALLAS.

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Since the early years of independence of the Central Asian states, and especially of Uzbekistan, the improvement of the mahalla activity, which was considered a traditional form of self-government, has gained great importance in the course of active socio-economic reforms in all areas. It has been given the status of a lower state body, a primary social organization, and its duties and tasks have been expanded. This was of great importance for revival of historical traditions of Central Asian nations and formation of spiritual and moral characteristics in the minds of citizens. The study of the activity of the mahalla, i.e. the neighborhood team in the family life of the Central Asian nations from the historical and ethnographic point of view is currently of great scientific importance. The tradition of living as a team dates back to the ancient periods of human history. According to historical data, in the late Paleolithic period, people's related collectives were formed, which lived together and shared common tools. In the course of the long historical evolution, these associations passed through certain stages and turned into a neighborhood team. Here it is necessary to mention the opinion of L. Levitin, who says: "Mahalla is the highest form of communal living in Uzbek society. This form of local collectives, local self-government has survived for centuries and was preserved at the points of sharp turns in Uzbek history. Today it has not yet fallen into oblivion.

The mahalla, prevalent in various Muslim regions, embodies a traditional neighborhood or district characterized by tight-knit communities, shared social customs, and a profound sense of identity. Mahallas, entrenched for centuries, hold significance in shaping the social, economic, and political fabric of Muslim societies. Often serving as the primary unit of local governance in many urban settings, they furnish essential services like education, healthcare, and security. Typically, centered around a mosque or religious institution, mahallas boast distinct customs and traditions. Residents foster a strong communal spirit, readily offering support to one another during times of adversity.

Despite encountering challenges like urbanization and economic shifts, many mahallas have adeptly adapted, remaining integral to Muslim community life.

Key Attributes of Mahallas:

- Strong community bonds
- Shared social and cultural practices
- Distinct identity
- Common association with religious centers
- Provision of various community services
- Deep-seated sense of belonging

Mahallas serve as invaluable cultural and social enclaves, exerting a profound influence on Muslim communities. Recognizing their unique traits underscores their significance, urging efforts toward their preservation for posterity. Mahallas are

undoubtedly architectural treasures, yet they encompass more than mere physical structures. While they often boast remarkable landmarks like historic residences, mosques, and public edifices, they also epitomize the intangible heritage of communal life, social structure, and cultural customs. Variety in architectural styles is a hallmark of mahallas, reflecting the historical, cultural, and religious influences of their inhabitants. Ranging from traditional adobe dwellings to elaborate mosques and mausoleums, mahallas embody the architectural evolution of their regions. Careful urban planning characterizes mahallas, fostering social interaction, pedestrian connectivity, and functional efficiency. With their labyrinthine lanes, shaded courtyards, and communal spaces, mahallas adhere to time-honored principles of Islamic urban design. Culturally, mahallas serve as custodians of heritage, preserving age-old customs, rituals, and practices. Festivals, ceremonies, and social gatherings within mahallas celebrate cultural identity and foster a sense of belonging among residents. Rooted in history, mahallas trace their origins back centuries, bearing witness to the passage of time and the lives of generations. They encapsulate the narratives of empires, dynasties, and everyday individuals who have called these neighborhoods home. At the core of mahallas lies vibrant community life, marked by solidarity, mutual aid, and shared values. Residents form tight-knit networks of families, neighbors, and friends, supporting one another through life's joys and challenges. Sustainability is ingrained in the fabric of traditional mahallas, with their compact layout, efficient resource use, and emphasis on communal living. From shared water sources to communal ovens and public baths, mahallas have long promoted sustainable practices. Despite facing challenges like urbanization and neglect, mahallas inspire adaptive reuse and conservation efforts. Communities actively strive to preserve their architectural and cultural heritage for future generations.

In essence, mahallas represent more than just architectural marvels; they are a testament to the resilience of communities, the richness of cultural traditions, and human creativity in shaping the built environment. As stewards of this invaluable legacy, it is incumbent upon us to cherish and safeguard mahallas for posterity.

Mahallas, as traditional neighborhoods or communities, have been of significant interest to architects, urban planners, and researchers due to their unique architectural features, social structures, and cultural significance. Here are some additional points about mahallas in architecture:

- **Architectural Features:** Mahallas typically feature narrow streets, courtyard houses, and compact urban layouts. The architecture is often designed to promote community interaction while providing privacy for individual households. Courtyard houses, for example, have a central courtyard surrounded by living spaces, which serve as private outdoor areas for families while also facilitating social gatherings.
- **Social Dynamics:** Mahallas are not just physical spaces but also social entities with strong community ties. The layout of streets and houses often reflects social hierarchies and cultural practices. Public spaces such as squares or mosques serve as focal points for community gatherings, religious activities, and cultural events.

- **Historical Evolution:** The development of mahallas is often influenced by historical, cultural, and environmental factors. Over time, they have evolved in response to changing social needs, economic conditions, and urbanization trends. Understanding the historical evolution of mahallas can provide insights into their resilience and adaptability.
- **Cultural Significance:** Mahallas are repositories of cultural heritage, embodying traditional architectural styles, craftsmanship, and community traditions. They often reflect the cultural identity and values of the people who inhabit them. Preserving and revitalizing mahallas is essential for maintaining cultural continuity and fostering a sense of belonging among residents.
- **Community Governance:** Mahallas often have their own governance structures, with informal leaders or councils responsible for managing local affairs. These grassroots governance systems play a crucial role in decision-making processes related to urban development, infrastructure maintenance, and conflict resolution. Understanding the dynamics of community governance within mahallas is essential for effective urban planning and development strategies.
- **Adaptive Design Principles:** Traditional mahalla architecture incorporates adaptive design principles suited to local climates and environmental conditions. Features such as shaded passageways, windcatchers, and water management systems reflect a deep understanding of environmental sustainability. Examining these traditional design strategies can inform contemporary approaches to sustainable urban design and climate resilience.
- **Cultural Practices and Rituals:** Mahallas are vibrant spaces where cultural practices and rituals are deeply ingrained in everyday life. Festivals, celebrations, religious ceremonies, and communal activities contribute to the social cohesion and identity of the neighborhood. Architects and urban planners interested in mahalla design should consider how cultural practices influence the built environment and vice versa.
- **Revitalization and Preservation:** Many historic mahallas face threats from urbanization, neglect, or redevelopment pressures. Efforts to revitalize and preserve these cultural heritage sites require careful consideration of conservation principles, community engagement, and sustainable development strategies. Architects and preservationists play a crucial role in advocating for the preservation of mahallas as living cultural landscapes.
- **Digital Documentation and Heritage Conservation:** Advances in digital technologies offer new opportunities for documenting, preserving, and disseminating knowledge about mahallas. Digital mapping, 3D modeling, virtual reality, and augmented reality tools can enhance our understanding of mahalla architecture and cultural heritage. These technologies can also support community-driven initiatives aimed at preserving and promoting the cultural significance of mahallas.
- **Identity and Place Attachment:** Mahallas are not just physical spaces but also places imbued with cultural identity and historical significance. Residents develop strong attachments to their mahallas, rooted in shared memories, traditions, and cultural practices. Understanding the intangible aspects of place attachment can

inform design interventions that respect and celebrate the unique identity of each mahalla.

- **Education and Advocacy:** Educating the public about the value of mahallas as cultural heritage sites and community assets is essential for their preservation and revitalization. Architectural schools, heritage organizations, and community groups can play a role in raising awareness about the significance of mahallas and advocating for their protection. Incorporating mahalla studies into educational curricula can inspire future generations of architects and planners to engage with these rich cultural landscapes.

- **Urban Morphology and Typology:** Mahallas often exhibit distinct urban morphologies and typologies that reflect their historical development, cultural influences, and social organization. Studying the spatial layout, building forms, and streetscape characteristics of different mahallas can reveal patterns of settlement, circulation, and land use. This understanding can inform urban design strategies that respect and enhance the unique identity of each mahalla while promoting functional and aesthetic coherence.

- **Heritage Conservation and Adaptive Reuse:** Many historic mahallas contain valuable architectural heritage that requires preservation and adaptive reuse. Balancing conservation objectives with the need for sustainable development and community revitalization is a complex task. Architects and preservationists must employ sensitive design interventions that respect the authenticity of historic fabric while accommodating contemporary needs and uses. Strategies such as adaptive reuse, heritage interpretation, and cultural tourism can breathe new life into historic mahallas while safeguarding their cultural significance.

- **Informal Urbanism and Participatory Design:** Mahallas often exhibit characteristics of informal urbanism, including self-built housing, informal economies, and bottom-up governance structures. Embracing the principles of participatory design and collaborative planning is essential for empowering communities to shape the future of their mahallas. Architects and planners should engage residents as active stakeholders in the design process, leveraging their local knowledge, aspirations, and priorities to co-create inclusive and sustainable urban environments.

- **Globalization and Urban Change:** Globalization, urbanization, and socio-economic transformations exert pressure on traditional mahallas, leading to processes of gentrification, displacement, and cultural homogenization. Understanding the dynamics of urban change and its impact on mahalla communities requires a nuanced analysis of economic forces, policy interventions, and cultural shifts. Architects and researchers can contribute to this discourse by investigating the spatial, social, and economic implications of globalization on mahalla environments and proposing strategies for mitigating negative effects while fostering resilience and cultural diversity.

- **Sustainability and Environmental Design:** Traditional mahallas often embody sustainable design principles that respond to local climatic conditions and resource constraints. Architects can draw inspiration from vernacular building techniques, passive design strategies, and indigenous materials used in mahalla

architecture to create environmentally responsive and energy-efficient buildings. Integrating green infrastructure, renewable energy systems, and water-sensitive design features into mahalla redevelopment projects can enhance resilience to climate change and promote ecological stewardship.

- **Cultural Landscapes and Memory scapes:** Mahallas are not only physical spaces but also cultural landscapes imbued with collective memories, narratives, and symbolic meanings. Understanding the concept of "memory scapes" in relation to mahallas involves recognizing how the built environment serves as a repository of cultural memory and identity for residents. Architects can engage with local communities to uncover hidden histories, oral traditions, and intangible heritage associated with mahalla spaces, informing design interventions that celebrate cultural diversity and promote intergenerational storytelling.

- **Adobe Construction:** Many traditional houses in old city Tashkent are constructed using adobe bricks made from locally sourced clay, straw, and sometimes animal dung. This traditional building material provides natural insulation, keeping the interior cool in the summer and warm in the winter.

- **Courtyard Design:** Traditional houses often feature a central courtyard, known as "iwan" or "ayvan," surrounded by rooms and living spaces. The courtyard serves as a private outdoor oasis, where families gather for meals, socialize, and relax.

- **Decorative Details:** Traditional Tashkent houses are adorned with intricate decorative details, including colorful ceramic tiles, carved wooden doors and window frames, and ornate plasterwork. These decorative elements reflect the city's rich cultural heritage and craftsmanship.

- **Historical Significance:** Many traditional houses in old city Tashkent date back several centuries and are considered historical landmarks. They provide insights into the architectural styles and lifestyle practices of past generations, contributing to the city's cultural identity and sense of place.

Traditional houses in Uzbekistan often feature distinctive architectural elements influenced by the region's history and climate. One of the most common types is the adobe house, made from sun-dried mud bricks, featuring flat roofs and ornate wooden doors and windows. Courtyards are also central to Uzbek architecture, providing privacy and serving as outdoor living spaces. Many traditional houses incorporate colorful ceramic tiles and intricate carvings, reflecting Uzbekistan's rich artistic heritage. Here are some additional details:

- **Iwan:** Traditional Uzbek houses often have an iwan, a large, covered porch or reception area, typically open on one side and supported by columns. The iwan serves as a welcoming space for guests and can be used for gatherings or relaxation.

- **Decorative Elements:** Uzbek architecture is known for its intricate decorative elements, including geometric patterns, arabesques, and floral motifs. These decorations adorn door frames, window shutters, and walls, adding beauty and character to the buildings.

- **Inner Courtyards:** Courtyards are a central feature of traditional Uzbek houses, providing a private outdoor space for families. Courtyards may feature gardens, fruit trees, and fountains, creating a peaceful oasis within the home.
- **Majolica Tiles:** Majolica tiles, known for their vibrant colors and intricate designs, are commonly used to decorate the facades of traditional Uzbek houses. These tiles often feature geometric patterns or floral motifs and are arranged in elaborate patterns, creating visually stunning exteriors.
- **Flat Roofs:** Traditional Uzbek houses typically have flat roofs, which are well-suited to the region's dry climate. Flat roofs also provide additional living space, with rooftop terraces often used for socializing or drying crops.

Despite the fact that as a result of intensive historical processes that took place throughout the 22nd century of Tashkent, both the geography and topography of this old city, and even its original name, have practically not changed, the historical landscape of the distant and recent past in terms of mahallas, buildings, structures, ilmgohlars and shrines that were subsequently formed on the territory of the present city of Tashkent, it has retained its expression to a certain extent. the others. (Figure1.1) For example, at the beginning of the XX century, according to some sources, there were only 281 mahallas, 180 mosques, 283 mosques, 26 madrassas in Tashkent. At present, there are more than ten thousand blocks in the cities of our republic, and 474 in the capital. There are about three thousand streets in the city.

Figure 1.1. Old city Tashkent in 1912

In the past, the borders of four other districts of Tashkent were defined along the central streets that crossed them longitudinally or transversely. And the mahallas were distinguished by their guzars. A number of buildings, mosques and madrasahs, and sometimes separate squares, were built along the streets and lakes laid out along the mahalla guzars. The toponymy of the city of Tashkent and its surroundings is diverse and, finally, rich in microtoponyms. At the beginning of the 20th century, for example, the city had up to 500 ponds, 1,500 bazaars, about 5,000 shops, 40 cemeteries and about 200 garden courts.

In 2019, work will begin on preserving the cultural layers that have developed over the centuries in the districts of the Old City of our capital. For this purpose, the project "District: urban and rural life" was developed and presented at the Venice Architecture Biennale.

According to the portal of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Foundation for the Development of Culture and Art in cooperation with UNESCO brought together leading scientists, specialists, architects and researchers. Life in the mahallas of Tashkent, architectural solutions are recognized by international experts as a way to revive eco-architecture, protect modern cities from mass urbanization, as well as preserve social values and community.